

Adverse events	Number of studies in meta-analysis	Events with dextropropripholone	Events with dexmedetomidine	Events with dexpropripholone	Effect N dexa (RR)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	P-value
Drowsiness	1	8	45	2	45 4	0,898	17,808	0,069
Bradycardia	2	16	90	6	90 2,551	0,868	7,499	0,089
Shivering	1	0	39	3	39 0,143	0,008	2,676	0,193
Neurological symptoms 24 hours	1	2	22	0	22 5	0,254	98,4	0,29
Oversedation	1	2	25	0	25 5	0,252	99,065	0,291
Persistent neurological symptoms 6 months	1	3	66	1	65 2,955	0,315	27,673	0,343
Persistent neurological symptoms 14 days	1	20	88	16	87 1,231	0,702	2,158	0,468
Horner syndrome	1	0	25	1	25 0,333	0,014	7,804	0,495
Constipation	1	1	39	0	39 3	0,126	71,428	0,497
Acute urinary retention	1	1	45	0	45 3	0,125	71,717	0,498
Hoarseness	1	4	91	6	90 0,657	0,194	2,219	0,498
Nausea	2	2	59	5	59 0,503	0,068	3,717	0,5
Shortness of breath	1	1	66	0	65 2,955	0,123	71,224	0,505
Vomiting	1	1	20	2	20 0,5	0,049	5,083	0,558
Syncope	1	1	39	2	39 0,5	0,047	5,291	0,565
General malaise	1	1	39	2	39 0,5	0,047	5,291	0,565
Hypotension	2	18	90	15	90 1,195	0,568	2,515	0,639
Paresthesia	1	3	25	2	25 1,5	0,274	8,22	0,64
Dizziness	3	9	104	8	104 0,884	0,204	3,827	0,869
PONV	3	9	106	9	106 1,012	0,309	3,314	0,984
Dyspnea	1	1	66	1	65 0,985	0,063	15,414	0,991
Pruritus	1	2	87	2	87 1	0,154	6,48	1
Vascular puncture	1	1	25	1	25 1	0,066	15,117	1
Bandage seep through	1	1	39	1	39 1	0,065	15,426	1
Hypoxemia	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Respiratory depression	0	0	45	0	45 NA	NA	NA	NA
Neurotoxicity	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Superficial soft tissue infection	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Tachycardia	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Chronic pain	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Over-sedation	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Hives	0	0	39	0	39 NA	NA	NA	NA
Fever	0	0	39	0	39 NA	NA	NA	NA

Reflux	0	0	39	0	39	NA	NA	NA	NA
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Adverse events	Number of studies in meta-analysis	Events with dexmed	N dexmed	Events with dexmed	N dexmed	Effect (RR)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	P-value
Hoarseness	1	4	66	7	66	0,571	0,176	1,86	0,353
PONV	1	10	29	13	29	0,769	0,404	1,465	0,425
Dizziness	1	0	20	1	20	0,333	0,014	7,713	0,493
Dyspnea	1	1	66	0	66	3	0,124	72,321	0,499
Nausea	1	2	20	1	20	2	0,197	20,332	0,558
Persistent neurological symptoms 14 days	1	20	66	17	66	1,176	0,679	2,038	0,562
Persistent neurological symptoms 6 months	1	3	66	4	66	0,75	0,175	3,222	0,699
Shortness of breath	1	1	66	1	66	1	0,064	15,654	1
Bradycardia	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Hypotension	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Hypoxemia	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Respiratory depression	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Vomiting	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Pruritus	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Neurotoxicity	0	0	20	0	20	NA	NA	NA	NA
Vascular puncture	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Paresthesia	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Horner syndrome	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Drowsiness	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Acute urinary retention	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Superficial soft tissue infection	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Tachycardia	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Chronic pain	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Over-sedation	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Shivering	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Neurological symptoms 24 hours	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Oversedation	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Constipation	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Syncope	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA

Hives	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
General malaise	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Fever	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Reflux	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Bandage seep through	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA

Adverse events	Number of studies in meta-analysis	Events with dexa + dexmed	Events		Effect (RR)	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	P-value
			N dexa + dexmed	N with placebo				
Shivering	1	0	39	4	41 0,117	0,006	2,099	0,145
PONV	2	6	61	12	63 0,54	0,204	1,429	0,214
Pruritus	1	2	42	0	42 5	0,254	98,4	0,29
Syncope	1	1	39	0	41 3,152	0,132	75,1	0,478
Hives	1	0	39	1	41 0,35	0,015	8,344	0,517
Fever	1	0	39	1	41 0,35	0,015	8,344	0,517
Reflux	1	0	39	1	41 0,35	0,015	8,344	0,517
Neurological symptoms 24 hours	1	2	22	3	22 0,667	0,123	3,609	0,638
Constipation	1	1	39	1	41 1,051	0,068	16,231	0,971
General malaise	1	1	39	1	41 1,051	0,068	16,231	0,971
Bandage seep through	1	1	39	1	41 1,051	0,068	16,231	0,971
Nausea	2	2	59	2	61 1,033	0,048	22,439	0,984
Bradycardia	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Hypotension	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Hypoxemia	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Respiratory depression	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Vomiting	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Dizziness	0	0	59	0	61 NA	NA	NA	NA
Neurotoxicity	0	0	20	0	20 NA	NA	NA	NA
Vascular puncture	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Paresthesia	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Hoarseness	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Horner syndrome	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Drowsiness	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA
Acute urinary retention	0	0	0	0	0 NA	NA	NA	NA

Superficial soft tissue infection	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Tachycardia	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Chronic pain	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Over-sedation	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Dyspnea	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Shortness of breath	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Persistent neurological symptoms 6 months	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
Persistent neurological symptoms 14 days	0	0	22	0	22	NA	NA	NA	NA
Oversedation	0	0	0	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA